

Example Data Management Plan – concise version

Linking routine data with clinical trial data to determine treatment outcomes from the ZEB34A clinical trial

Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) Example Data Management Plan

Concise version

Organisation
ELIXIR-UK

Created by

Liz
Merrifield
id [0009-0001-5416-0216](#)

Based on

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I. Data areas and data types

A retrospective quantitative, secondary analysis, data linkage study, linking clinical trial participant data with data from the National Trusted Databank (NTD) to determine survival outcomes. This project will link clinical trial data with death data made available through the National Trusted Databank, a Trusted Research Environment.

II. Standards and metadata

Standard metadata, produced as per the ZEB34A clinical trial, will be utilised for this secondary analysis study. Details of the methodologies used to characterise and analyse the primary data will be recorded. All outputs from this project will be accompanied by appropriate documentation, code commenting and update to resources design for these purposes. This project follows UK Data Service guidelines for describing qualitative data.

III. Relationship to other data available in public repositories

Data in this project comes from two sources – the ZEB34A clinical trial, managed by the CTU and routine death data provided by the ONS through the NTD. Data for the ZEB34A main clinical trial have been uploaded into the ISRCTN registry. All study records for the primary dataset are freely accessible and searchable.

IV. Secondary use

Due to this project being a secondary analysis of clinical trial data and linked routine data, data controllership and consent model this project is limited for additional analysis, and the subsequent utility of this data may also be limited. The primary datasets are under the Data Controllership of the University Clinical Trials Unit (CTU), whereby the University is the designated Sponsor and data controller. Access to these primary datasets may be accessed through negotiation with the University CTU.

V. Methods for data sharing

Following publication, we will publish the data from this sub-study to the ISRCTN Registry to ensure reusability and accessibility of these findings, citing the main ZEB34A clinical trial, which is also listed within this publicly accessible registry. ISRCTN registry

attributes a unique object identification (UOI) number, which may be referenced in future citations.

VI. Proprietary data

ZEB34A clinical trial participants provided research consent for anonymised data to be shared with approved projects for future research. Due to this sub-study project being a secondary analysis of clinical trial data, data controllership and consent model, this project is limited for additional analysis, and the subsequent utility of this data may also be limited.

VII. Timeframes

Data will be shared in a timely manner and shared publicly at the time of its publication, or within one year from the project end date.

VIII. Format of the final dataset

The final pseudonymised will be prepared for long-term storing, with consideration to conversion and future use. Data will be stored in csv format as an open, standard, interchangeable and longer-lasting format, thus maximising the potential for future utility. For long-term digital preservation, the University data centres archive data in open and standard formats.